

Studies on some 3d metal complexes – Synthesis, spectroscopic characterization and biological studies

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A novel tridentate Schiff base ligand was prepared from 3-acetylcoumarin and 2-aminobenzoic acid. This ligand is versatile in forming complexes with manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) ions. The ligand and the metal complexes were characterized through various physicochemical and spectral studies. These studies include elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, UV-Vis, IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and ESR spectral studies wherever possible and applicable. The spectral data revealed that the ligand acted as monobasic tridentate, coordinating to the metal ion through the azomethine nitrogen, lactone carbonyl oxygen and carboxylate oxygen. The fluorescence spectra of the ligand and its metal complexes in DMSO were also recorded. The powder X-ray diffraction pattern showed the crystalline nature of the ligand and its copper(II) complex. The ligand possessed an orthorhombic crystal structure and on complexation the crystal system is changed to tetragonal. The ligand and the metal complexes were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities and it has been observed that the metal complexes are more potent bactericides and fungicides than the ligand. The α -amylase inhibitory activity of the ligand and metal complexes was also examined. In this case also chelation enhanced the α -amylase inhibitory activity.

Keywords: 3-Acetylcoumarin, Schiff base, XRD, fluorescence, antibacterial activity, antifungal activity, α -amylase inhibitory activity.

Introduction

Metal complexes of Schiff bases are considered to be among the most important stereochemical models in main group and transition metal coordination chemistry mainly because of their synthetic proclivity, structural diversities and versatility offered by these complexes in their potential applications in biological, clinical, analytical and pharmacological fields¹. A combination of distinctly different metal ion binding sites within one ligand can lead to formation of materials with interesting new properties, e.g. specific sensors, molecular wires and optical devices^{2,3}. Schiff bases and their metal complexes have exhibited interesting biological activities^{4,5}. In some Schiff base complexes, it has been observed that minor changes in the structure of the ligands containing hard/soft donor atoms, e.g. nitrogen, sulfur, and/or oxygen markedly affect the activity of the compounds^{6,7}. Schiff bases and their metal complexes

have been used as drugs and reported to possess significant activities against bacteria, fungi, and certain type of tumors⁸⁻¹². Schiff bases derived from coumarin derivatives are of special interest, because coumarin derivatives have been reported to possess a wide variety of pharmacological activities, such as anti-coagulants, antibacterial agents, antifungal agents, biological inhibitors, chemotherapeutics and as bio-analytical reagents¹³⁻¹⁵. They are useful antioxidants and show antitumor activity and cytotoxicity^{16,17}. In view of the importance of coumarin Schiff bases, we have isolated and characterized some new transition metal complexes of a potential tridentate Schiff base viz. 3-[1-{N-(2-carboxyphenyl)imino}ethyl]coumarin (HNAA) derived from 3-acetylcoumarin and 2-aminobenzoic acid. In this communication, we describe the synthesis, characterization, antimicrobial activities and α -amylase inhibitory activity studies on some 3d-metal complexes of the newly synthesized Schiff base.

Results and discussion

Reaction between transition (II) metal salts and the ligand can be symbolized by the following equations:

The ligand formed well-defined complexes with Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} salts. All the complexes are stable at room temperature and possess good keeping qualities. Analytical data of the complexes are in good accord with their formulation as in Table 1 (Supplementary data). Formulation of these complexes has been made based on their elemental analysis and molar conductance measurements. Molar conductance values of the complexes measured in different solvents adequately confirm the non-electrolytic nature of the metal complexes¹⁸.

band accompanied by the appearance of two characteristic bands at 1535–1548 cm^{-1} and 1323–1347 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO})$ respectively and the separation between $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO})$ in metal complexes was more than 200 cm^{-1} . This is a clear evidence for the coordination of carboxylate group in all the complexes in a monodentate fashion^{21,22}. The free ligand exhibits a strong band at 1676 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ lactone²³. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ of lactone shifts to lower wavenumber by 70–85 cm^{-1} in all complexes indicating the involvement of lactone oxygen in coordination. The bonding of the ligand to the metal ion is further supported by the appearance of new bands in the regions 470–485 cm^{-1} , 415–425 cm^{-1} and 352–362 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to the $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})$ bands respectively in the far IR spectra of the metal complexes^{13,19}. These observations give added support that the ligand binds the metal ion in a tridentate manner, through

Table 1. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of the ligand and its metal complexes

Compd.	MIC Value ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)				MIC ₅₀ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Streptococcus</i>	<i>Klebsiella</i>	<i>Pseudomonas</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>
HNAA	100	50	100	100	51.97
[Mn(NAA) ₂]	100	50	50	50	48.006
[Co(NAA) ₂]	50	50	50	50	34.5
[Ni(NAA) ₂]	100	50	100	100	28.106
[Cu(NAA)Cl]	12.5	50	25	25	36.54
[Zn(NAA)Cl]	50	50	50	50	34
Streptomycin	7.5	15	7.5	15	–
Clotrimazole	–	–	–	–	2.5
DMSO (solvent)	–	–	–	–	–

Infrared spectra:

The IR spectrum of the Schiff base showed a characteristic peak at 1609 cm^{-1} assignable to C=N stretching frequency of the azomethine group. On complexation, this peak was shifted to lower frequency by 15–25 cm^{-1} in all the metal complexes, indicating coordination of azomethine nitrogen with the metal ion¹⁹. The intense band at 1738 cm^{-1} present in the IR spectrum of the free ligand may be assigned to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ of carboxylic group^{20,21}. Spectra of the metal complexes show the absence of this

azomethine nitrogen, carboxylate oxygen and lactone carbonyl oxygen atom.

¹³C and ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance spectra:

The ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra for the ligand and the zinc(II) complex were recorded with TMS as the standard. The proton NMR spectrum of the ligand shows peaks in the region 7.4–8.65 ppm and 10.3 ppm due to the aromatic protons and the carboxylic proton respectively^{19,21}. In the ¹H NMR spectrum of the zinc(II) complex, the -COOH peak is not observed. This is a clear evidence for coordination of

carbonyl group after deprotonation. In the ^{13}C NMR spectra of the ligand and the zinc(II) complex there is a downfield shift in the absorption for the -COOH carbon, lactone carbonyl carbon and the -C=N carbon atom in the zinc(II) complex compared to the ligand. This chemical shift is attributed to the removal of electron density around the bonded carbon atom due to coordination. This shows that the carboxylate oxygen, lactone carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen are participating in the formation of the metal complex. The rest of the absorptions are not altered.

Electronic spectra:

The electronic spectra of the ligand exhibited two absorption bands at 287 nm and 330 nm due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions respectively of the azomethine group. On complexation, this band was shifted to lower wavelength region suggesting the coordination of azomethine nitrogen to the central metal ion. The solid reflectance spectral data of the ligand and the complexes were measured. The electronic spectrum of the manganese(II) complex exhibited weak absorption bands for the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(v_2)$ (525 nm) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(v_3)$ (400 nm). These absorptions are consistent with an octahedral geometry around manganese(II) in the complex. The magnetic moment values of the manganese(II) complex is 6.03 B.M., suggesting an octahedral geometry²⁴. The electronic spectrum of cobalt(II) complex exhibits two absorption bands corresponding to transitions around 570 nm and 471 nm assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. The magnetic moment value of cobalt(II) complex, 4.94 B.M., along with the electronic spectral data suggests an octahedral geometry around the cobalt(II) ion^{25,26}. The electronic absorption spectrum of nickel(II) complex shows weak bands at 572 nm and 415 nm which are assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. The magnetic moment value of nickel(II) complex, 3.4 B.M., together with the electronic spectral data suggests an octahedral geometry around the nickel(II) ion^{27,28}. The copper(II) complex shows bands at 652 nm, which is assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transition. The copper(II)

complex has a magnetic moment value of 1.84 B.M., which is in good agreement with a square planar geometry²⁶. Zinc(II) complexes are diamagnetic and a tetrahedral geometry is most preferable for four coordinated zinc(II) complex²⁹.

EPR spectra:

The EPR spectrum of copper(II) complex indicates a distorted square-planar geometry to the complex. The X band spectrum of copper(II) complex was recorded at room temperature (Fig. 1) and at liquid nitrogen temperature. The spectrum shows axial symmetry with well $g_{||}$ and g_{\perp} values ($g_{||} = 2.25$, $g_{\perp} = 2.10$). The trend $g_{||} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ indicates that the unpaired electron is most likely in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital¹⁰. The fact that $g_{||}$ value is less than 2.3 is an indication of significant covalent character. The geometric parameter G , which is a measure of the exchange interaction between copper centers in a polycrystalline compound is calculated using the equation $G = (g_{||} - 2.0023)/(g_{\perp} - 2.0023)$. The value of G (2.53) less than four suggests that the interaction between metal centers is considerable and the local tetragonal axes are misaligned³⁰.

Fig. 1. ESR spectrum of copper(II) complex (at room temperature).

The EPR spectrum of manganese(II) complex was recorded as polycrystalline material and in DMSO solution. In the solid state and at room temperature (Fig. 2), the ESR spectrum of manganese(II) complex shows a strong signal centered at $g = 2.0227$. In frozen DMSO solution, the spectra consist in six

Fig. 2. ESR spectrum of manganese(II) complex (at room temperature).

hyperfine lines, typical of monomeric manganese(II) complexes.

The EPR spectrum of cobalt(II) complex was recorded as polycrystalline sample. The spectrum was not clear at room temperature because of the rapid spin lattice relaxation of cobalt(II) broadens the lines. However, the cobalt(II) complex exhibited a very broad signal at liquid nitrogen temperature with g values 6.13 and 3.15. The deviation of g values from the free electron value (2.0023) may be due to angular momentum contribution in the complex.

Cyclic voltammetry:

Cyclic voltammetry is the most extensively used technique for acquiring qualitative information about electrochemical reactions. The electrochemical behavior of copper(II) complex was examined by means of CV employing glassy carbon as the working electrode, Ag/AgCl as reference electrode and platinum wire as the auxiliary electrode. The working media consisted of DMSO and Bu_4NPF_6 as supporting electrolyte. The solution was degassed with argon prior to use and kept under argon atmosphere throughout the experiment. All measurements were carried out using 2 mM solution at room temperature in the potential range -2.0 to $+2.0$ V with a scan rate 80 mV s^{-1} . In the forward scan an anodic current peak at about 305 mV corresponds to oxidation process of copper(II) complex ($\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$). In the reverse scan CV profile displayed two waves at E_{pc} values $+240$

Fig. 3. Structure of the ligand.

Fig. 4. Structure of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes.

Fig. 5. Structure of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes.

mV and -780 mV corresponding to the reversible reduction of the metal complex and irreversible reduction of the ligand respectively. The peak currents for both cathodic and anodic peak are recorded. The peak separation (ΔE_p) is found to be 65 mV and the ratio of the anodic to cathodic peak current ($I_{\text{pa}}/I_{\text{pc}}$) is found to be approximately equal to unity. This is a clear evidence for one electron transfer in the electrode reaction^{31,32}. From these observations it is concluded that the redox process is diffusion controlled and demetallation of copper(II) complex is not involved.

Fluorescence spectral studies-emission spectroscopy:

The excitation and emission spectra of all the complexes and ligand in DMF at room temperature have been recorded (Fig. 6). The excitation wavelength was fixed at 300 nm and the emission spectra were recorded in the range 320–580 nm. Schiff base ligand exhibits an emission maximum at 330 nm, which undergoes a red shift to 395–400 nm upon complexation. The emission spectra are recorded for all the metal complexes using the same solvent. The red shift of the emission maximum of the complexes (λ_{em}) compared with the Schiff base may be due to the deprotonation of the carboxylic group. Deprotonation

Fig. 6. Fluorescence spectra of the ligand and metal complexes.

blocks excited state proton transfer (ESPT) and can lead to enhancement in fluorescence intensity as well as spectral shifts³³. On complexation fluorescence intensity enhances. The introduction of the Schiff base enlarges the π -conjugated system of the complex and enhances the luminescent intensity of the complex³⁴. The higher fluorescence intensity of complexes compared to the ligand may be attributed to increased rigidity of the ligand on coordination thereby reducing the loss of energy by thermal vibrational decay. The fluorescence emission intensity of Schiff base decrease upon complex formation with metal ion in the order: $Zn^{II} > Mn^{II} > Co^{II} > Cu^{II} > Ni^{II}$. The zinc(II) complex exhibit highest fluorescence emission which may be due to its stable d^{10} configuration. The ligand shows highly selectivity towards zinc over other metal ions. Because zinc(II) has a closed-shell d^{10} electronic configuration, we can expect that its coordination would alleviate photo-induced electron transfer (PET) more effectively and provide enhanced fluorescence³⁵.

Powder XRD study:

The X-ray diffractograms of the Schiff base ligand and the copper(II) metal complex were scanned from 5° to 80° . The diffractograms of both the ligand and the complex indicate high crystallinity. The diffractogram of the ligand has recorded 15 reflections with maxima at $2\theta = 9.3689^\circ$ which corre-

sponds to the interplanar distance, $d = 9.43993 \text{ \AA}$. The ligand has been successfully indexed to orthorhombic crystal system with lattice constants $a = 18.8578 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 6.6356 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 4.9774 \text{ \AA}$ and cell volume = 622.8335 \AA^3 . From the XRD pattern of the copper(II) complex, it is observed that the crystallinity is retained even after complexation. The diffractogram has recorded 23 reflections of 2θ ranging from 7.07° to 53.22° with a maximum at $2\theta = 7.07^\circ$ which corresponds to interplanar distance $d = 12.502 \text{ \AA}$. The complex has also been indexed to a tetragonal crystal system with lattice constants $a = 12.4924 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 12.4924 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.6688 \text{ \AA}$ and the cell volume = 1040.73 \AA^3 . The average crystalline size of the ligand and the copper(II) complex are calculated using the Scherrer formula,

$$d_{\text{xrd}} = 0.9 \lambda / \beta \cos \theta$$

The particle sizes have been found to be 64 nm and 31 nm for the ligand and the metal complex, respectively³⁶.

Antimicrobial activity:

The MIC values of the ligand and its metal complexes against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and the fungus *Candida albicans* are given in the Table 1. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of the ligand and its metal complexes compared with those of the standard drugs Streptomycin and Clotrimazole respectively. The antimicrobial activities are presented in the table showing that the free ligand and all metal complexes exhibit antibacterial activity against both strains. Study of antifungal activity of the ligand and its metal complexes revealed that all the metal chelates are more toxic than the ligand. Metal complexes exhibit higher antimicrobial activity than free ligand under identical experimental conditions. The higher activity of the metal complexes may be due to the effect of metal ions on the normal cell membrane³⁶. Enhancement of activity of ligand after chelation can be explained on the basis of chelation theory³⁷. Chelation reduces the polarity of the metal ion to a considerable extent due to the partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups and possible π electron delocalization

over the whole chelate ring. Lipids and polysaccharides are some important constituents of cell walls and membranes, which are preferred for metal ion interaction. Reduction in polarity in turn increases the lipophilic character of the chelate and the interaction between the metal ion and the lipid is favored. This may result in breaking down of the permeability barrier of the cell and interference with the normal cell processes. The Cu^{II} complex shows good activity against all the tested microbial strains ($\text{MIC} \leq 50 \mu\text{g/mL}$). Percentage inhibition was found to be increasing with the concentration of the ligand and metal complexes.

The antimicrobial activity of the metal complexes cannot be attributed to chelation alone, but it is a complex blend of several other important factors such as nature of the metal ion, nature of the ligand, coordinating sites, geometry of the complex, concentration, hydrophilicity, lipophilicity and presence of coligands. Steric and pharmacokinetic factors also play decisive role in deciding the potency of an antimicrobial agent¹². This may be the reason for the variations in the activity of different complexes against different organisms.

α -Amylase inhibitory activity studies:

The α -amylase inhibitory properties of the ligand and complexes are presented in Fig. 7. In the human

species, α -amylase is present in both salivary and pancreatic secretions. α -Amylase digests carbohydrates (polysaccharides) into smaller disaccharide units, eventually converting them into monosaccharides such as glucose so that they can be used by the body. The inhibition activity of α -amylase might be responsible for decreasing the rate of glucose absorption and concentration of postprandial serum glucose^{38,39}. This effect would delay the degradation of starch and oligosaccharides, which would in turn cause a decrease in the absorption of glucose and consequently inhibit the increase in postprandial blood glucose⁴⁰. The IC_{50} values for the ligand and its metal complexes were given in the Table 2. The α -amylase inhibitory effectiveness of the ligand and the complexes were compared with the standard Acarbose based on their resulting IC_{50} values.

The α -amylase inhibitory activity data reveals that the ligand is a poor α -amylase inhibitor. On complexation, the amylase inhibitory activity enhances. The detected inhibition of α -amylase activity may be owed to the interaction of active sites of the enzyme with the potential sites of the metal complexes. The inhibitory activity of the metal complexes is greatly influenced by the positioning of potential sites of the ligand around the metal ion. As the coordination number of the central metal atom increases the num-

Fig. 7. α -Amylase inhibitory activity of the ligand and metal complexes.

Table 2. α -Amylase inhibitory activity of the ligand and metal complexes: The IC_{50} values

Compd.	IC_{50} (mg/mL)
Acarbose	0.112
HNAA	1.48
[Mn(NAA) ₂]	0.122
[Co(NAA) ₂]	0.884
[Ni(NAA) ₂]	0.443
[Cu(NAA)Cl]	0.491
[Zn(NAA)Cl]	0.804

ber of stereo isomers possible increases, thereby the ability of the metal center to organize substituents in the three-dimensional space increases substantially⁴¹. This leads to increase in interaction between the active sites of the enzyme and the metal complex. The inhibitory activity has been found to be increased in the order, ligand < cobalt < zinc < copper < nickel < manganese. Among metal complexes manganese(II) complex possess highest inhibitory activity.

Thermogravimetric analysis:

The copper(II) complex was subjected to the thermal decomposition study from ambient temperature to 800°C (Fig. 8). The complex was thermally stable upto 260°C and decomposed in three stages. The TG curve shows no weight loss up to 260°C, indicating the absence of coordinated water. The first decomposition stage at 260–295°C with mass loss

Fig. 8. TG profile of copper(II) complex.

32.69% (Calcd. 33.17%) attributed to the loss of anthranilic acid moiety of the ligand. The second stage of decomposition in the range 295–355°C corresponds to the loss of C₄H₄ part of the ligand and chlorine atom, followed a mass loss of 21.92% (Calcd. 21.67%). The third stage, starts from 355°C and ends at 515°C, showed a mass loss of 29.35% (Calcd. 29.70%) corresponding to the loss of remaining part of the ligand and the oxidation of the metal to CuO which was stable above this temperature. The final product was identified as CuO by X-ray diffraction analysis. Apart from evaluating the thermal stability of metal complexes this study also helps in the formulation of complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. Commercial solvents were distilled and used for synthesis. For physicochemical measurements, the solvents were purified by standard methods. Carbon, hydrogen, and nitrogen and analyses were performed using Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108-CHN Analyser ElementarSysteme, Vario EL III CHN analyser and the metal contents in the complexes were determined using a Nulab GBC 902 atomic absorption spectrophotometer in an acetylene/air flame. Molar conductance measurements were conducted using 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in appropriate solvents at room temperature with a Systronic model 304 digital conductivity meter. Infrared spectral studies were carried out using a Thermo-Nicolet Avatar 370 FT-IR spectrophotometer and electronic spectra were recorded on a Hitachi 320 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The NMR spectra of the ligand and the zinc(II) complex were recorded on a JEOL GSX 400 MHz FT NMR spectrometer employing TMS as internal reference and CDCl₃ as solvent. The EPR spectra of the metal complexes were recorded using a JES - FA200 ESR spectrometer with X band employing manganese as reference material. Cyclic voltammetric study of the copper(II) complex was performed on a BSI SP-200 CV analyzer. X-Ray diffraction experiments were carried out on a Siemens D 5005 model spectrometer. Thermal decomposition studies were carried out using a Mettler Toledo thermogravimetric

balance in dynamic air, at a heating rate of 10°C/min.

Synthesis of the ligand:

To a solution of 2-aminobenzoic acid (0.01 mol) in ethanol, 3-acetylcoumarin (0.01 mol) in ethanol was added dropwise. The above mixture was refluxed for 3 h and cooled at room temperature. The crystals separated were filtered, washed successively with ethanol and ether, recrystallized from ethanol (70% yield, m.p. 110°C).

Synthesis of metal complexes:

The metal complexes were prepared by the following general procedure: To a hot ethanolic solution (100 ml) of the ligand, ethanolic solution of metal(II) salt (20 mL) was added in small portions in the appropriate ratio. The pH of the solution was maintained between 6.5–7.5 by adding alcoholic ammonia solution and the mixture was heated to reflux for 4 h. Then the volume of the solution was reduced to half of its initial volume and allowed to cool. The solid complex separated was filtered off and washed successively with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum.

Antimicrobial screening:

Antibacterial activity of free ligand and its metal complexes, was tested *in vitro* against Gram-positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans*) and Gram-negative bacteria (*Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) by agar-well diffusion method. In agar-well diffusion method the antimicrobials present in the samples are allowed to diffuse out into the medium and interact in a plate freshly seeded with the test organisms. The resulting zones of inhibition will be uniformly circular as there will be a confluent lawn of growth. The diameter of zone of inhibition can be measured in centimeters. Petriplates containing 20 ml Muller Hinton Agar Medium were seeded with bacterial culture of *Pseudomonas*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Streptococcus* and *Staphylococcus aureus*⁴². Wells of approximately 10 mm was bored using a well cutter and sample of different volumes such as 6.25, 12.5, 25, 50 and 100 µL were added. The plates were then incubated

at 37°C for 24 h. The antibacterial activity was assayed by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone formed around the well. MIC values were determined. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) is the lowest concentration of an antimicrobial that inhibits visible bacterial growth.

The antifungal activity of the ligand and its complexes were determined *in vitro* against the fungus *Candida albicans* by serial dilution method⁴³. The anti-candida activity of the ligand and the metal complexes was expressed as MIC₅₀ values (the minimum concentration required to inhibit 50% of cells growth) specified in the table. In serial dilution method samples were dissolved in DMSO to a final concentration of 1 mg/ml and added in increasing concentrations such as 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50 µg respectively and incubated overnight at 37°C. Growth was observed by visual inspection and by measuring the optical density (OD) at 620 nm using a spectrophotometer. The OD was measured immediately after the visual reading. The growth inhibition for the test wells at each sample dilution was determined by the formula:

$$\text{Percent inhibition} = \frac{(\text{OD of control} - \text{OD of test})}{(\text{OD of control})} \times 100\%$$

The minimum and maximum values were 0% and 100%, respectively. Streptomycin and Clotrimazole were the standards for antibacterial and antifungal activities.

α-Amylase inhibition assay:

α-Amylase inhibitory activity was determined by the method described by the Worthington Enzyme Manual⁴⁴ with slight modification. Different concentrations of 10 mg/ml sample and make up to 100 µL using 25 mM phosphate buffer pH 6.9, containing 25 µL of porcine α-amylase at a concentration of 0.5 mg/ml were incubated at 25°C for 10 min. After pre-incubation, 25 µL of 0.5% starch solution in 25 mM phosphate buffer pH 6.9 was added. The reaction mixtures were then incubated at 25°C for 10 min. The reaction was stopped with 50 µL of 96 mM 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid colour reagent. The micro plate was then incubated in a boiling water

bath for 5 min and cooled to room temperature. Absorbance was measured at 540 nm using a microplate reader. The α -amylase inhibitory activity was calculated per the equation given below:

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = (A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}) / A_{\text{control}} \times 100$$

where A_{control} was the absorbance of the control (without the compound), A_{sample} was the absorbance in the presence of the compound.

Conclusion

Based on the physicochemical and spectral data discussed above, the following structures have been assigned for the 1:1 and 1:2 metal complexes: Octahedral geometry for manganese(II), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes and square planar and tetrahedral geometry for copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes respectively. IR spectra show the ligand as a monobasic, ONO tridentate, coordinating via carboxylic oxygen, imino nitrogen and lactone carbonyl oxygen. Thermal study reveals that the copper(II) complex is thermally stable. XRD study suggests tetragonal crystal system for copper(II) complex. The ligand and its metal complexes are biologically active; antimicrobial activity shows that the copper(II) complex has the highest activity. The result of α -amylase inhibitory activity study reveals that manganese(II) complex exhibits highest inhibition potential compared to other metal complexes.

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